

**International Journal of Computer Networks &
Communications (IJCNC)**

(Scopus, ERA Listed)

ISSN 0974 - 9322 (Online); 0975 - 2293 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijcnc.html>

**Current Issue: November 2018, Volume
10, Number 6 --- Table of Contents**

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijc2018.html>

PERFORMANCE OF OLSR MANET ADOPTING CROSS-LAYER APPROACH UNDER CBR AND VBR TRAFFICS ENVIRONMENT

Teerapat Sanguankotchakorn¹, Sanika K.Wijayasekara² and Sugino Nobuhiko³

¹Asian Institute of technology, Thailand, ²Chulalongkorn University, Thailand and
³Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan

ABSTRACT

The routing protocols play an important role in Mobile Ad-Hoc Network (MANET) because of the dynamically change of its topology. Optimized Link State Routing (OLSR), unawareness of Quality of Service (QoS) and power-consumed protocol, is an example of a widely-used routing protocol in MANET. The Multi-Point Relays (MPR) selection algorithm is very crucial in OLSR. Therefore, firstly, we propose a heuristic method to select the best path based on two parameters; Bit Error Rate (BER) derived from the physical layer and Weighted Connectivity Index (CI) adopted from the network layer. This can be done via the cross-layer design scheme. This is anticipated to enhance the performance of OLSR, provide QoS guarantee and improve the power consumption. The performances of the proposed scheme are investigated by simulation of two types of traffics: CBR and VBR (MPEG-4), evaluated by metrics namely Throughput, Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), Average End-to-End Delay, Control Overhead and Average Total Power Consumption. We compare our results with the typical OLSR and OLSR using only Weighted CI. It is obvious that our proposed scheme provides superior performances to the typical OLSR and OLSR using only Weighted CI, especially, at high traffic load.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Ad-hoc Network (MANET), OLSR, Bit Error Rate (BER), Weighted Connectivity Index, Quality of Service (QoS).

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcnc/V10N6/10618cnc01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijc2018.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Hui-Hsiang Khao, Peng-Jung Wu, Chung-Nun Lee, "[Analysis and Enhancement of Multi-channel MAC Protocol for Ad Hoc Networks](#)", International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol. 24, pp. 310-324, 2011.
- [2] Rony Ohayon, "Virtual Reservation Scheme for Supporting CBR Multimedia Services with Strict QoS Performance over WLAN and Wireless Mesh", International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol.25, pp.571-584, 2012.
- [3] Saoucene Mahfoudh and Pascale Minet, "An Energy Efficient Routing Based on OLSR in Wireless Ad Hoc and Sensor Networks", The 22nd IEEE International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications, IEEE Computer Society, pp.1253-1259, 2008.
- [4] Ren-Hung Wang, Chiung-Ying Wang, Chi-Jen Wu and Guan-Nan Chen, "[A Novel Efficient Powersaving MAC Protocol for Multi-hop MANETs](#)", International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol.26, pp.34-55, 2013.
- [5] Y.Chen, T.Farley and N.Yel, "QoS Requirements of Network Applications on the Internet", Information-Knowledge-Systems Management, pp.55-76,2004.
- [6] T. Sanguankotchakorn, Sanika K. Wijayasekara and Nobuhiko Sugino, "[A Cross-layer Design Approach in OLSR MANET using BER and Weighted Connectivity Index](#)", The 19th IEEE International Conference on Networks (ICON2013), Orchard Hotel, Singapore, pp.1-6, December 11th-13th, 2013.
- [7] C.E.Perkins and E.M.Royer: "Ad-hoc On-demand Distance Vector Routing", The 2nd IEEE Workshop on Mobile Computing System and Applications (WMCSA), pp.99-100, February 1999.
- [8] K.Kunavut and T. Sanguankotchakorn: "[Optimized Path Selection Process in OLSR Based on Weighted Connectivity Index and Delay](#)", The 8th International Conference on Electrical Engineering/Electronics, Computer, Telecommunications and Information Technology (ECTI-CON 2011), pp. 348-351, May 2011.
- [9] T.Yelemou, P.Meseure and A.-M. Poussard: "A new BER-based Approach to improve OLSR Protocol", The 8th International Conference on Wireless and Optical Communications Networks (WOCN 2011), pp. 1-5, May 2011.
- [10] T. Clausen and P. Jacque: "[Optimized Link State Routing Protocol \(OLSR\)](#)", Technical Report ,RFC3626, IETF Network Working Group, October 2003.
- [11] J.Leguay, V.Conan and T.Friedman: "[QoS Routing in OLSR with Several Classes of Service](#)", The 4th Annual IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications Workshops 2006 (PerCom Workshops 2006), pp. 420-425, March 2006.

- [12] A.Amani, Y.Fakhri and J.Abouchabak: "[QoS Routing and Performance Evaluation for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks Using OLSR Protocol](#)", International Journal of Ad hoc Sensor and Ubiquitous Computing (IJASUC), Vol.2, No.2, June 2011.
- [13] K. Kunavut and T. Sanguankotchakorn: "[QoS-aware Routing for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks Based on Multiple Metrics: Connectivity Index \(CI\) and Delay](#)", The 7th International Conference on Electrical Engineering/Electronics Computer Telecommunications and Information Technology 2010 (ECTICON 2010), pp. 46-50, May 2010.
- [14] K. Kunavut and T. Sanguankotchakorn: "[Multi-Constrained Path \(MCP\) QoS routing in OLSR Based on Multiple Additive QoS Metrics](#)", International Symposium on Communications and Information Technologies 2010 (ISCIT 2010), pp. 226-231, October 2010.
- [15] K.Kunavut and T.Sanguankotchakorn:"[Generalized Multi-constrained Path \(G MCP\) QoS Routing for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks](#)", Journal of Communications, Vol.7, No.3, pp.246-257, March 2012.
- [16] Ram S. Dahal and T. Sanguankotchakorn: "[QoS Routing in MANET through Cross-Layer Design with BER and Modifying AODV](#)", Asian Himalayan International Conference on Internet (AHICI2011), The next Generation of Mobile, Wireless and Optical Communication Networks, Kathmandu, Nepal, November 4-6, 2011.
- [17] H.Badis, A.Mavaretto, K.A.Agha and G.Pujolle, "[Optimal Path Selection in a Link State QoS Routing Protocol](#)", Proceeding of IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference, Vol.4, pp.2570-2574, May 2004.
- [18] GeYing, T.Kunz and L. Lamont: "[Quality of Service Routing in Ad-hoc Networks using OLSR](#)", Proceedings of the 36th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences 2003,pp. 9, January 2003.
- [19] X. Yuan, "[Heuristic Algorithms for Multi-Constrained Quality-of-Service Routing](#)", IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking, Vol.10, Issue 2, pp.244-256, 2002.
- [20] P.Khadivi, S.Samavi and T.D. Todd," [Multi-constraint QoS Routing using a new Single Mixed Metrics](#)", Journal of Network and Computer Applications, Vol.31, Issue 4,pp.656-676, 2008.
- [21] Dong-won Shin, Edwin K.P. Chong and Howard Jay Siegel, "[Multi-Post path-based Look ahead Multi-Constraint QoS Routing](#)", Journal of the Franklin Institute, Vol.349, Issue 3, pp.1106-1124, 2012.
- [22] Jiann-Liang Chen, Shih-Wei Liu, SZu-Lin Wu and Ming-Chiao Chen, "[Cross-layer and Cognitive QoS Management System for Next Generation Networking](#)", International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol. 24, pp.1150-1162, 2011.

- [23] Min Chen, Liang Zhou, Takahiro Hara, Yang Ziao and Victor C.M. Leung", [Advances in Multimedia Communications](#)", International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol.24, pp.1243-1245, 2011.
- [24] Li-Feng Zhou, Lei Chen, Hung Keng Pung and Lek Heng Ngoh, "[Identifying QoS Violations through Statistical End-to-End Analysis](#)" ,International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol.24, pp.1388- 1406, 2011.
- [25] Jin Ye, Jian-xin Wang and Jia-wei Huang, "[A Cross-layer TCP for providing Fairness in Wireless Mesh Network](#)", International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol.24, pp.1161-1626, 2011.
- [26] Qiong Shi, Cristina Comaniciu, Dandan Wang and UfukTureli, "[Cross-layer MAC Design for Location aware Wireless Sensor Networks](#)", International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol. 24, pp.872-888, 2011.
- [27] Weifeng Sun, Tong Fu, Feng Xia, Zhenquan Qin and Rong Cong, "[A Dynamic Channel Assignment Strategy based on Cross-layer Design for Wireless Mesh Networks](#)", International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol. 25, pp.1122-1138, 2012.
- [28] Kun Yang, Xueqi Cheng and Giovanni Pau, "Interdisciplinary and Cross-layer Design of Mobile Social Networks and Wireless Networks", International Journal of Communication Systems, Vol.25, pp.1243-1244, 2012.
- [29] T. Sanguankotchakorn, S. Shrestha and N.Sugino, "[Effective Social Ad Hoc Networking on OLSR MANET using Similarity Approach](#)", The 5th International Conference in Internet and Distributed Computing Systems (IDCS2012), pp.15-28, November 2012.
- [30] V. Srivastava. and M. Motani: "Cross-Layer Design: A Survey and the Road Ahead",IEEE Communications Magazine, Vol.43, No.12, pp. 112-119, December 2005.
- [31] Marco Fotino and Floriano De Rango, "[Energy Issues and Energy aware Routing in Wireless Ad-hoc Networks](#)", <http://www.intechopen.com/books/mobile-ad-hoc-networks-protocol-design/energyissues-and-energy-aware-routing-in-wireless-ad-hoc-networks> ", pp.281-296, 2011.
- [32] A.Kumar and Q.M.Rafiq and K.Bansal, "[Performance Evaluation of Energy Consumption in MANET](#)", International Journal of Computer Application, Vol .42, No.2, pp.7-12 , March 2012.
- [33] Jun Huang, Xiaohong Huang, Yan Ma, "Routing with Multiple Quality-of-Services Constraints: An Approximation Perspective", Journal of Network and Computer Applications, Vol. 35, Issue 1, pp. 469-479, 2012.
- [34] Kirti Aniruddha Adoni and Radhika D. Joshi, "[Optimization of Energy Consumption for OLSR Routing Protocol in MANET](#)", International Journal of Wireless and Mobile Networks, Vol.4, No.1, pp.251-262, February 2012.

- [35] Adel Aneiba and Mohammed Melad, "[Performance Evaluation of AODV, DSR, OLSR, and GRP MANET Routing Protocols Using OPNET](#)", International Journal of Future Computer and Communication, Vol.5, No.1, pp. 57-60, February, 2016
- [36] K.Kunavut and T.Sanguankotchakorn," [Performance Evaluation of Ad Hoc Routing Protocols to Deliver MPEG-4 Traffic](#)", The 12th IEEE International Conference on Communication Technology (ICCT2010), pp.207 -210,November 2010.
- [37] W.Xiuchao, "[Simulate 802.11b Channel within NS2](#)", Technical Report, URL: http://read.pudn.com/downloads165/doc/756173/Simulate_802.11b_Channel_NS2.pdf, NUS,2004.
- [38] Fall, K. and Varadhan, K: "[Formerly NS Notes and Documentation](#)", UC Berkeley, USC/ISI and Xerox PARC, November, 2011.
- [39] The Network Simulator-ns- 2, <http://www.isi.edu/nsnam/ns>
- [40] C.-H.Ke, and C.-K.Shieh, W.-S. Hwang, and A. Ziviani," [An Evaluation Framework for More Realistic Simulations of MPEG Video Transmission](#)", Journal In Information Science and Engineering, pp.425-440, 2008.

AUTHORS

Teerapat Sanguankotchakorn was born in Bangkok, Thailand on December 8, 1965. He received the B. Eng in Electrical Engineering from Chulalongkorn University, Thailand in 1987, M. Eng and D. Eng in Information Processing from Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan in 1990 and 1993, respectively. In 1993, he joined Telecommunication and Information Systems Research Laboratory at Sony Corporation, Japan where he holds two patents on Signal Compression. Since October 1998, he has been with Asian Institute of Technology where he is currently an Associate Professor at Telecommunications Field of Study, School of Engineering and Technology. He is a Senior member of IEEE and member of IEICE, Japan.

Sanika K. Wijayasekara was born in Sri Lanka on January 14, 1986. She received her B.Sc.(Hons) in IT specialized in Computer System and Networking degree from Sri Lanka Institute of Information Technology, Sri Lanka in 2010 and M.Sc in Telecommunications from Asian Institute of Technology, Thailand in 2012. Her current research interests are in the area of Cross-Layer designs, QoS assurances in multimedia applications and wireless network protocols.

Nobuhiko Sugino was born in Yokkaichi, Mie, Japan on November 19, 1964. He received B. Eng, M. Eng, and D.Eng. in Physical Electronics from Tokyo Institute of Technology in 1987, 1989 and 1992, respectively. Since 1992, he has been with Tokyo Institute of Technology, where is now an Associate Professor at Department of Information System, Interdisciplinary Graduate School of Science and Engineering. Dr. Nobuhiko Sugino is a member of IEICE and IEEE.

IMPROVEMENT OF FALSE REPORT DETECTION PERFORMANCE BASED ON INVALID DATA DETECTION USING NEURAL NETWORK IN WSN

Sanghyeok Lim and Taeho Cho

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Sungkyunkwan University,
Republic of Korea

ABSTRACT

WSN consists of a number of nodes and base stations and is used for event monitoring in various fields such as war situations, forest fires, and home networks. WSN sensor nodes are placed in fields that are difficult for users to manage. It is therefore vulnerable to attackers, and attackers can use false nodes or MAC injection attacks through the hijacked nodes to reduce the lifetime of the network or trigger false alarms. In order to prevent such attacks, several security protocols have been proposed, and all of them have been subjected to MAC-dependent validation, making it impossible to defend against false report attacks in extreme attack circumstances. As attacks have recently become more diverse and more intelligent, WSNs require intelligent methods of security. Based on the report information gathered from the base station, the proposed method provides a technique to prevent attacks that may occur where all MAC information is damaged by carrying out verification of a false report attack through the machine learning based prediction model and the evaluation function.

KEYWORDS

Network Protocols, Wireless Sensor Network, simulation, machine learning, neural network.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcnc/V10N6/10618cnc02.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijc2018.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Al-Karaki, Jamal N., and Ahmed E.Kamal. "[Routing techniques in wireless sensor networks: a survey](#)." IEEE wireless communications 11.6 (2004): 6-28.
- [2] Perrig, Adrian, John Stankovic, and David Wagner. "[Security in wireless sensor networks](#)." Communications of the ACM 47.6.
- [3] Karlof, Chris, and David Wagner. "[Secure routing in wireless sensor networks: Attacks and countermeasures](#)." Sensor Network Protocols and Applications, 2003. Proceedings of the First IEEE. 2003 IEEE International Workshop on. IEEE, 2003.
- [4] Padmavathi, Dr G., and Mrs Shanmugapriya. "[A survey of attacks, security mechanisms and challenges in wireless sensor networks](#)." arXiv preprint arXiv:0909.0576 (2009).
- [5] Pathan, Al-Sakib Khan, Hyung-Woo Lee, and Choong Seon Hong. "[Security in wireless sensor networks: issues and challenges](#)." Advanced Communication Technology, 2006. ICACT 2006. The 8th International Conference. Vol. 2. IEEE, 2006.
- [6] Li, Feng, and Jie Wu. "[A probabilistic voting-based filtering scheme in wireless sensor networks](#)." Proceedings of the 2006 international conference on Wireless communications and mobile computing. ACM, 2006
- [7] Zhu, Sencun, et al. "[An interleaved hop-by-hop authentication scheme for filtering of injected false data in sensor networks](#)." Security and privacy, 2004. Proceedings. 2004 IEEE symposium on. IEEE, 2004
- [8] Yang, Hao, and Songwu Lu. "[Commutative cipher based en-route filtering in wireless sensor network](#)." Vehicular Technology Conference, 2004. VTC2004-Fall. 2004 IEEE 60th. Vol. 2. IEEE, 2004.
- [9] Yu, Zhen, and Yong Guan. "[A dynamic en-route scheme for filtering false data injection in wireless sensor networks](#)." Proceedings of the 3rd international conference on Embedded networked sensor systems. ACM, 2005
- [10] Hagan, Martin T., et al. Neural network design. Vol. 20. Boston: Pws Pub., 1996.
- [11] Adeli, Hojjat, and Shih-Lin Hung. Machine learning: neural networks, genetic algorithms, and fuzzy systems. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1994.
- [12] Haykin, Simon S., et al. Neural networks and learning machines. Vol. 3. Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA:: Pearson, 2009.
- [13] Weiss, Sholom M., and Casimir A. Kulikowski. Computer systems that learn: classification and prediction methods from statistics, neural nets, machine learning, and expert systems. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., 1991.

- [14] Krizhevsky, Alex, Ilya Sutskever, and Geoffrey E. Hinton. "[Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks.](#)" Advances in neural information processing systems. 2012.
- [15] Kubat, Miroslav, Robert C. Holte, and Stan Matwin. "[Machine learning for the detection of oil spills in satellite radar images.](#)" Machine learning 30.2-3 (1998): 195-215.
- [16] Sebastiani, Fabrizio. "[Machine learning in automated text categorization.](#)" ACM computing surveys (CSUR) 34.1 (2002): 1-47.
- [17] Bradley, Andrew P. "[The use of the area under the ROC curve in the evaluation of machine learning algorithms.](#)" Pattern recognition 30.7 (1997): 1145-1159.
- [18] Nasrabadi, Nasser M. "[Pattern recognition and machine learning.](#)" Journal of electronic imaging 16.4 (2007): 049901.
- [19] Bak, Per, Kan Chen, and Chao Tang. "[A forest-fire model and some thoughts on turbulence.](#)" Physics letters A 147.5-6 (1990): 297-300.
- [20] Preisler, Haiganoush K., and Alan A. Ager. "[Forest-Fire Models.](#)" Encyclopedia of environmetrics 3 (2006).
- [21] Anderson, D. H., et al. "[Modelling the spread of grass fires.](#)" The ANZIAM Journal 23.4 (1982): 451-466.
- [22] Weber, R. O. "[Modelling fire spread through fuel beds.](#)" Progress in Energy and Combustion Science 17.1 (1991): 67-82.
- [23] Soares-Filho, Britaldo Silveira, Gustavo Coutinho Cerqueira, and Cássio Lopes Pennachin. "DINAMICA—a stochastic cellular automata model designed to simulate the landscape dynamics in an Amazonian colonization frontier." Ecological modelling 154.3 (2002): 217-235.
- [24] Mallet, Daniel G., and Lisette G. De Pillis. "[A cellular automata model of tumor-immune system interactions.](#)" Journal of theoretical biology 239.3 (2006): 334-350.
- [25] Dijkstra, Jan, Joran Jessurun, and Harry JP Timmermans. "[A multi-agent cellular automata model of pedestrian movement.](#)" Pedestrian and evacuation dynamics (2001): 173-181.
- [26] Karafyllidis, Ioannis, and Adonios Thanailakis. "[A model for predicting forest fire spreading using cellular automata.](#)" Ecological Modelling 99 (1997): 87-97.
- [27] Encinas, A. Hernández, et al. "[Simulation of forest fire fronts using cellular automata.](#)" Advances in Engineering Software 38.6 (2007): 372-378.
- [28] Karafyllidis, Ioannis. "[Design of a dedicated parallel processor for the prediction of forest fire spreading using cellular automata and genetic algorithms.](#)" Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence 17.1 (2004): 19-36.

- [29] Wolfram, Stephen. "[Universality and complexity in cellular automata.](#)" Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena 10.1-2 (1984): 1-35.
- [30] Nam, Su Man, and Tae Ho Cho. "[Context-aware architecture for probabilistic voting-based filtering scheme in sensor networks.](#)" IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing 16.10 (2017): 2751-2763.
- [31] Song and Lee, 2013: Sensitivity Analysis on Ecological Factors Affecting Forest Fire Spreading: Simulation Study Korean Journal of Agricultural and Forest Meteorology, Vol. 15, No. 3 pp. 178~185
- [32] Agostinelli, Forest, et al. "[Learning activation functions to improve deep neural networks.](#)" arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6830 (2014).
- [33] Le, Quoc V., et al. "[On optimization methods for deep learning.](#)" Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on International Conference on Machine Learning. Omnipress, 2011.
- [34] Srivastava, Nitish, et al. "[Dropout: a simple way to prevent neural networks from over fitting.](#)" The Journal of Machine Learning Research 15.1 (2014): 1929-1958.
- [35] Munir, Saad Ahmed, et al. "[Mobile wireless sensor network: Architecture and enabling technologies for ubiquitous computing.](#)" Advanced Information Networking and Applications Workshops, 2007, AINAW'07. 21st International Conference on. Vol. 2. IEEE, 2007.

AUTHORS

Sanghyeok Lim Received a B.S. degree in Digital Information Engineering from Hanguk University of Foreign Studies in 2017, and is now working toward an M.S. degree in the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering at Sungkyunkwan University.

Taeho Cho Received a Ph.D. degree in Electrical and Computer Engineering from the University of Arizona, USA, in 1993, and B.S. and M.S. degrees in Electrical and Computer Engineering from Sungkyunkwan University, Republic of Korea, and the University of Alabama, USA, respectively. He is currently a Professor in the College of Information and Communication Engineering, Sungkyunkwan University, Korea.

SCALABLE AND ENERGY EFFICIENT TASK OFFLOADING SCHEMES FOR VEHICULAR CLOUD COMPUTING

Mohammad Pasha¹ and Khaleel Ur Rahman Khan²

¹Department of Information Technology, MJCET, Hyderabad, India

²Department of Computer Science Engineering, ACE, Hyderabad, India

ABSTRACT

Smart vehicles of today on road are equipped with advanced computational units, multiple communication technologies, intelligent sensing platforms, and human-computer interaction devices which utilize Vehicular Edge Networks to support services offered by the remote cloud. This being named as Opportunistic Vehicular Edge Computing recently, has the possibility to supplement the services provided by the Edge gadgets. Many Vehicular Edge Computing architectures have been proposed as of late which support task offloading. One among the premier difficulties in these networks is efficiently utilizing the resources available at the vehicular nodes. The present work uses APEATOVC, a conveyed and versatile protocol for economical, efficient and effective task offloading in these networks which address the adaptability of vehicular clouds. The results obtained by extensive simulations are presented to assess and contrast its performance with existing protocols.

KEYWORDS

Vehicular Cloud Computing, Mobile Edge Computing, Vehicular Ad-Hoc Networks, Computation Offloading.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcnc/V10N6/10618cnc03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijc2018.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Hu, Yun Chao, et al. "[Mobile edge computing—A key technology towards 5G.](#)" ETSI white paper 11.11 (2015): 1-16.
- [2] Fernando, Nirosinie, Seng W. Loke, and Wenny Rahayu. "[Mobile cloud computing: A survey.](#)" Future generation computer systems 29.1 (2013): 84-106.
- [3] Sardellitti, Stefania, Gesualdo Scutari, and Sergio Barbarossa. "[Joint optimization of radio and computational resources for multicell mobile-edge computing.](#)" IEEE Transactions on Signal and Information Processing over Networks 1.2 (2015): 89-103.
- [4] Uzcátegui, Roberto A. "Universidad Nacional Experimental Politécnica "[Antonio José de Sucre](#)" Guillermo Acosta-Marum." Georgia Institute of Technology "WAVE: A Tutorial" TOPICSIN Automotive Networking (2009).
- [5] Abdelhamid, Sherin, Hossam S. Hassanein, and Glen Takahara. "[Vehicle as a mobile sensor.](#)" Procedia Computer Science 34 (2014): 286-295.
- [6] Chen, Lei, and Cristofer Englund. "[Cooperative intersection management: a survey.](#)" IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems 17.2 (2016): 570-586.
- [7] Shojafar, Mohammad, Nicola Cordeschi, and Enzo Baccarelli. "[Energy-efficient adaptive resource management for real-time vehicular cloud services.](#)" IEEE Transactions on Cloud computing (2016).
- [8] Adhikary, Tamal, et al. "[Quality of service aware reliable task scheduling in vehicular cloud computing.](#)" Mobile Networks and Applications 21.3 (2016): 482-493.
- [9] Turcanu, Ion, et al. "[DISCOVER: a unified protocol for data dissemination and collection in VANETs.](#)" Proceedings of the 12th ACM Symposium on Performance Evaluation of Wireless Ad Hoc, Sensor, & Ubiquitous Networks. ACM, 2015.
- [10] Liu, Kai, et al. "[Cooperative data scheduling in hybrid vehicular ad hoc networks: VANET as a software defined network.](#)" IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking (TON) 24.3 (2016): 1759-1773.
- [11] Ye, Tianpeng, et al. "[A Safety Resource Allocation Mechanism against Connection Fault for Vehicular Cloud Computing.](#)" Mobile Information Systems 2016 (2016).
- [12] Ghazizadeh, Puya, et al. "[Towards fault-tolerant job assignment in vehicular cloud.](#)" Services Computing (SCC), 2015 IEEE International Conference on. IEEE, 2015.
- [13] Orsini, Gabriel, Dirk Bade, and Winfried Lamersdorf. "[Computing at the mobile edge: Designing elastic android applications for computation offloading.](#)" IFIP Wireless and Mobile Networking Conference (WMNC), 2015 8th. IEEE, 2015.
- [14] Whaiduzzaman, Md, et al. "[A survey on vehicular cloud computing.](#)" Journal of Network and Computer Applications 40 (2014): 325-344.
- [15] Zhao, Dong, et al. "[Opportunistic coverage for urban vehicular sensing.](#)" Computer Communications 60 (2015): 71-85.
- [16] Chaâri, Rihab, et al. "[Cyber-physical systems clouds: A survey.](#)" Computer Networks 108 (2016): 260-278.

- [17] Li, Bo, et al. "[Computation offloading management for vehicular ad hoc cloud.](#)" International Conference on Algorithms and Architectures for Parallel Processing. Springer, Cham, 2014.
- [18] Van Le, Duc, and Chen-Khong Tham. "[A deep reinforcement learning based offloading scheme in ad-hoc mobile clouds.](#)" IEEE INFOCOM 2018-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS). IEEE, 2018.
- [19] Alfaqawi, Mohammed IM, et al. "[Adaptive load balancing algorithm for wireless distributed computing networks.](#)" Intelligent Systems Engineering (ICISE), 2016 International Conference on. IEEE, 2016.
- [20] Lee, Won-II, et al. "[Relative velocity based vehicle-to-vehicle routing protocol over ad-hoc networks.](#)" International Journal of Ad Hoc and Ubiquitous Computing 12.1 (2013): 14-22.
- [21] Sommer, Christoph, Reinhard German, and Falko Dressler. "[Bidirectionally coupled network and road traffic simulation for improved IVC analysis.](#)" IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing 10.1 (2011): 3-15.
- [22] Varga, András, and Rudolf Hornig. "[An overview of the OMNeT++ simulation environment.](#)" Proceedings of the 1st international conference on Simulation tools and techniques for communications, networks and systems & workshops. ICST (Institute for Computer Sciences, Social-Informatics and Telecommunications Engineering), 2008.
- [23] Krajzewicz, Daniel, et al. "[SUMO \(Simulation of Urban MObility\)-an open-source traffic simulation.](#)" Proceedings of the 4th middle East Symposium on Simulation and Modelling (MESM20002). 2002.
- [24] Klingler, Florian, Falko Dressler, and Christoph Sommer. "[IEEE 802.11 p unicast considered harmful.](#)" Vehicular Networking Conference (VNC), 2015 IEEE. IEEE, 2015.
- [25] Barceló, Jaume. "[Models, traffic models, simulation, and traffic simulation.](#)" Fundamentals of traffic simulation. Springer, New York, NY, 2010. 1-62.
- [26] Gramaglia, Marco, et al. "[New insights from the analysis of free flow vehicular traffic in highways.](#)" World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks (WoWMoM), 2011 IEEE International Symposium on a. IEEE, 2011.
- [27] Moon, YoungJu, et al. "[A slave ants based ant colony optimization algorithm for task scheduling in cloud computing environments.](#)" Human-centric Computing and Information Sciences 7.1 (2017): 28.
- [28] Zhou, Bowen, et al. "[An Online Algorithm for Task Offloading in Heterogeneous Mobile Clouds.](#)" ACM Transactions on Internet Technology (TOIT) 18.2 (2018): 23.
- [29] Volkov, Bc Nikolay. "[Resource allocation for vehicular cloud computing.](#)" management 27.5 (2018): 48-55
- [30] Jiang, Zhiyuan, et al. "[Task Replication for Deadline-Constrained Vehicular Cloud Computing: Optimal Policy, Performance Analysis, and Implications on Road Traffic.](#)" IEEE Internet of Things Journal 5.1 (2018): 93-107.

A NOVEL ADAPTIVE CACHING MECHANISM FOR VIDEO ON DEMAND SYSTEM OVER WIRELESS MOBILE NETWORK

Saleh Ali Alomari

Faculty of Sciences and Information Technology, Jadara University, Irbid, Jordan

ABSTRACT

Video on Demand (VOD) system over the wireless mobile network is a system that provides video services to mobile clients. The main problem with these systems is the high service delay where the mobile clients have to wait to view their favorite movie. The importance of this paper is based on finding a solution on how to reduce the delay time in the VOD system. This paper introduces a novel caching mechanism named Proxy Server Cache mechanism to tackle the issue of service delay. This delay happens when the broadcasting phase that is related to the first segment is missed by a client from the current broadcasting channels. In this mechanism, the video's first segment is stored on a server of a stationary proxy type. The delayed clients will directly acquire the first segment from the proxy server instead of waiting for the following broadcasting channel pertaining to the first segment. The proposed scheme ensures obtaining the first segment from mobile clients when they arrive. Additionally, the performance of the proposed scheme is validated by applying the VOD system, which can involve the balancing mechanism to retain particular requests through to the local proxy server to provide a fair dissemination for these requests. The obtained result confirms that the proposed scheme reduces the time delay of the system in comparison with the best existing schemes. The results of the average time delay in the Proxy-Cache scheme is 179.2505 milliseconds when 10 clients arrive each minute (Client/minute), the average time delay is 140 milliseconds when the video lengths are 30, 60 and 90. Meanwhile, the failure probability for obtaining the first segment of the video remains zero when the number of arrived requests is set to 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10.

KEYWORDS

VOD, Proxy-Cache, All-Cache, PoR-Cache, Random-Cache, DSC-Cache, SB, LF's, LPS

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcnc/V10N6/10618cnc04.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijc2018.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Duc AT, Think N. (2008). [Broadcasting Techniques for Video-on-Demand in Wireless Networks. Book Chapter 1](#), department of Computer Science, University of Dayton, Dayton, OH 45469. Oregon State University, Corvallis, OR 97331.
- [2] Gruber S, Rexford J, Basso A. (2000). Protocol considerations for a pre-caching proxy for multimedia streams, in Proc. of the 9th International WWW Conference, pp. 657-668.
- [3] Park YW, Baek KH, Chung KD.(2000). Reducing network traffic using two-layered cache servers for continuous media on the internet, in Proc.Of the IEEE Int'l Conf. on Computer Software and Applications, pp. 389-394.
- [4] Duc AT, Minh L, Kien AH. (2004). [MobiVoD: A Video-on Demand System Design for Mobile Ad hoc Networks](#). Proceedings of the 2004 IEEE International Conference on MobileData Management (MDM'04). Berkeley, CA, pp. 212 223.
- [5] Saleh Ali Alomari, Putra Sumari. (2010). [A Video on Demand System Architecture for Heterogeneous Mobile Ad Hoc Networks for Different Devices](#). International Conference on Computer Engineering and Technology, Vol.7, pp.700 – 707.
- [6] Saleh Ali Alomari, Putra Sumari. (2012). [A Novel Optimized Design of Popularity Cushion Staggered Broadcast over Video on Demand System](#). International Journal of Physical Sciences Vol. 7, No.9, pp. 1435 - 1453, 23 February, 2012
- [7] Li-Shen J, Li-Ming T. (1998). Fast data broadcasting and receive scheme for popular video service. IEEE transactions on broadcasting, Vol. 44, No. 1, 1998.
- [8] Paris JF, Carter SW, Long DDE. (1999). [A hybrid broadcasting protocol for video on demand](#). In Proc. 1999 Multimedia Computing and Networking Conference, San Jose, CA, pp: 317-326.
- [9] kien AH, Simon S. (1997) [skyscraper broadcasting, A new broadcasting scheme for metroplitan Video on Demand systems](#). In Proceedings of ACM SIGCOMM 1997, Cannes, France.
- [10] Hee J, Seong-min J, Sung-kwon P, Seung-hwan S, Dong-hwa Y. (2008). Interleaving harmonic staggered broadcasting scheme for video-on-demand services. Tenth IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia.
- [11] Kwon JB, Heom HY. (2002).[Providing vcr functionality in staggered video broadcasting](#). IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics, Vol.48, No.1, pp.41–48.
- [12] GuiYQ, Jung E, Choi Y, Choi HK. (2007). an efficient periodic broadcast scheme for mobile video –on demand system “In Proc. International Conference on Information Technology, pp. 888-889.

- [13] L. Juhn and L. Tseng. Harmonic broadcasting for video-on-demand service. IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting, Vol 43, No.3, pp.268–271.
- [14] Saleh Ali Alomari, Putra Sumari, Sadik Ali Taweel. (2011). [An Efficient Popularity Cushion Staggered Broadcasting for Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Mobile Video-on-Demand System](#). International Conference on Wireless and Optical Communications, Vol.4, pp.272-277.
- [15] Saleh Ali Alomari and Putra Sumari.,(2012), Effective Broadcasting and Caching Technique for Video on Demand over Wireless Mobile Network. KSII Transactions on Internet and Information Systems (TIIS), Vol. 6, No. 3, pp. 919- 940.
- [16] R. Asorey and F.J. Gonzalez Castano, “A Multicast nVoD Schema with Zero-Overhead Implicit Error Correction,” in Proc. Of IEEE ICC 2008, pp. 2017-2020, May. 2008.
- [17] A. Dan, D. Sitaram and P. Shahabuddin. Scheduling policies for an on demand video server with batching. In Proc. 6th Int'l. Multimedia Conf. (ACM Multimedia'94), San Francisco, CA, , pp.15-23.
- [18] K. A. Hua, Y. Cai and S. Sheu. Patching: [A multicast technique for true video-on-demand services. In Proc.](#) 6th ACM Int'l. Multimedia Conf. (ACM Multimedia '98), Bristol, U.K., pp 191-200.
- [19] Z. Fei, I. Kamel, S. Mukherjee, and M. H. Ammar, “Providing Interactive Functions for Staggered Multicast Near Video-on-Demand Systems,” Proc. IEEE Conf. on Multimedia and Computing Systems (ICMCS99), pages 949-953, 1999.
- [20] K.A. Hua, S. Sheu, [Skyscraper broadcasting: a new broadcasting scheme for metropolitan video-on demand systems](#), Proceedings SIGCOMM 97, pp. 98 100, 1997.
- [21] L. Juhn, L. Tseng, Harmonic broadcasting protocols for video on demand service, IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting 43 (3) pp.268-271, 1997.
- [22] L. Juhn, L. Tseng, Fast data broadcasting and receiving scheme for popular video service, IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting 44 (1) pp.100– 105. 1998.
- [23] Liao, W. and Li, V. O. K. (1997). [The split and merge protocol for interactive video on demand](#). IEEE Multimedia , Vol. 4, No. 4, pp.51-62.
- [24] Paramasiven A, (2011)., SAMPCAN: A novel caching technique for Client-server interaction model in large ad hoc networks Using resampling methods, International Journal of Wireless & Mobile Networks (IJWMN) Vol. 3, No. 2, April 2011.
- [25] Xie F, Hua K. (2009). A caching-based video-on-demand service in wireless relay networks. IEEE International Conference on Wireless Communications and Signal Processing, , pp. 1– 5.
- [26] Subhabrata S, Jennifer YR, Don T. (1999). [Proxy Prefix Caching for Multimedia Streams](#) , CMPSCI Technical Report 98-27 University of Massachusetts.

- [27] Saleh Ali Alomari, Putra Sumari. (2010). A new Peer to Peer Caching Techniques for Transmitting the Video over Wireless Ad Hoc Network. (IJCSIS) International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, Vol. 8, No. 3, pp. 239-245.
- [28] Saleh Ali Alomari, and Putra Sumari (2014). "[PSCM: Proxy Server Cache Mechanism for VOD System](#)" International Conference on Communications, Signal Processing and Computers (CSPC 2014). Interlaken, Switzerland, February 22-24 2014.(ISSN: 1790-5117) PP: 138-144.
- [29] Saleh Ali Alomari, Putra Sumari. (2010). A Video on Demand System Architecture for Heterogeneous Mobile Ad Hoc Networks for Different Devices. International Conference on Computer Engineering and Technology, Vol.7, pp.700 – 707.
- [30] Vaithegy D, Saleh Ali Alomari, Putra S. (2011). [Video on Demand Caching System using NIPBCS over Mobile Ad Hoc Network](#), JDCTA: International Journal of Digital Content Technology and its Applications, Vol.5, No.6, pp. 142 -154.
- [31] Georgios S. Paschos, George Iosifidis., (2018)., [The Role of Caching in Future Communication Systems and Networks](#), IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, Special Issue on Caching for Communication Systems and Networks, 2018.
- [32] G. Paschos, E. Bastug, I. Land, G. Caire and M. Debbah, (2016)., "[Wireless Caching: Technical Misconceptions and Business Barriers](#)," IEEE Communications Magazine, vol. 54, no. 8, pp. 16-22.
- [33] K. Zhang, C. Tian, (2018)., "[Fundamental Limits of Coded Caching: From Uncoded Prefetching to Coded Prefetching](#)", IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, Special Issue on Caching for Communication Systems and Networks, 2018.
- [34] J. Sahoo, M. A. Salahuddin, R. Glitho, H. Elbiaze, and W. Ajib, (2017)., "[A Survey on Replica Server Placement Algorithms for Content Delivery Networks](#)", IEEE Communications Surveys And Tutorials, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 1002-1026, 2017.
- [35] C.SriguruLakshmi, G.sivakumar, V.Venkatachalam, (2013)., [Survey on caching and replication Algorithm for content distribution In peer to peer networks](#), International Journal of Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology (IJCSEIT), Vol.3,No.5,October 2013.
- [36] Hua, K. A and Sheu, S. (1998). [An efficient periodic broadcast technique for digital video libraries](#), Journal of Multimedia Tools and Applications, Vol. 5, No.3, pp.1-20.
- [37] Liu, W. C. and Jack, Y. B. (2003). Constrained Consonant Broadcasting – A Generalized Periodic Broadcasting Scheme for Large Scale Video streaming. Proceedings IEEE International Conference on Multimedia & Expo, Baltimore, U.S.A, Vol.1 pp.805-808.
- [38] Branch, P., Egan, G. and Tonkin, B. (1999)., A client caching scheme for interactive video-on-demand, Proceedings in IEEE International Conference on Networks, pp. 391 – 397.

AUTHOR

Saleh Ali Alomari obtained his MSc and Ph.D. in Computer Science from Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM), Pulau Penang, Malaysia in 2008 and 2013 respectively. He is a lecturer at the Faculty of Science and Information Technology, Jadara University, Irbid, Jordan. He is Assistance Professor at Jadara University, Irbid, Jordan 2013. He was the head of the Computer Network Department at Jadara University from 2014 until 2016. He is the candidate of the Multimedia Computing Research Group, School of Computer Science, USM. He is research assistant with Prof. Dr. Putra, Sumari. He is managing director of ICT Technology and Research and Development Division (R&D) in D&D Professional Consulting Company, Malaysia. He has published over 40 papers in international journals and refereed conferences at the same research area. He is a member and reviewer of several international journals and conferences (IEICE, ACM, KSII, JDCTA, IEEE, IACSIT, etc). His research interest is in the area of multimedia networking, video communications system design, multimedia communication specifically on Video on Demand system, P2P media streaming, MANETs, caching techniques and for advanced mobile broadcasting networks as well.

AVAILABILITY ASPECTS THROUGH OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES BASED OUTLIER DETECTION MECHANISM IN WIRELESS AND MOBILE NETWORKS

Neeraj Chugh, Adarsh Kumar and Alok Aggarwal

School of Computer Science, University of Petroleum & Energy Studies, Dehradun, India

ABSTRACT

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) and Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) are the two most prominent wireless technologies for implementing a complete smart environment for the Internet of Things (IoT). Both RFID and WSN are resource constraint devices, which forces us to go for lightweight cryptography for security purposes. Security in terms of confidentiality, integrity, authentication, authorization, and availability. Key management is one of the major constraints for resource constraint mobile sensor devices. This work is an extension of the work done by Kumar et al. using efficient error prediction and limit of agreement for anomaly score. This work ensures cryptographic property, availability, in RFID-WSN integrated network through outlier detection mechanism for 50 to 5000 nodes network. Through detection ratios and anomaly scores system is tested against outliers. The proposed outlier detection mechanism identifies the inliers and outliers through anomaly score for protection against Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack. Intruders can be detected in few milliseconds without giving any conflict to the access rights. In terms of throughput, a minimum improvement of 6.2% and a maximum of 219.9% is observed for the proposed protocol as compared to Kumar et al. Protocol and in terms of percentage of Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), a minimum improvement of 8.9% and a maximum of 19.5% is observed for the proposed protocol as compared to Kumar et al. protocol.

KEYWORDS

WSN, MANET, RFID, ANOMALY, SECURITY

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijenc/V10N6/10618cnc05.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijc2018.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Kumar, K. Gopal and A. Aggarwal, "[Outlier Detection and Treatment for Lightweight Mobile Ad Hoc Networks](#)," in In International Conference on Heterogeneous Networking for Quality, Reliability, Security and Robustness, Greater Noida, India, 11-12 January 2013, pp. 750-763.
- [2] A. Kumar, A. Agarwal and Charu, "[Efficient Hierarchical Threshold Symmetric Group Key Management Protocol for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks](#)," Inter. Conf. on Contemporary Computing – IC3 2012, Noida, India, 6-8 August 2012, pp. 335-346.
- [3] D. Bonch and M. Franklin, "[Identity-based encryption from weil pairing](#)," Advances in Cryptology-Crypto 2001, Santa Barbara, California, USA, August 2001, pp. 213-229.
- [4] Merwe, J. V. D., D. D. and M. S., "[A survey on peer-to-peer key management for mobile ad hoc networks](#)," ACM computing surveys (CSUR), Vol. 39, No. 1, 1, April 2007, pp. 1-45.
- [5] H. Deng, A. Mukherjee and D. Aggarwal, "[Threshold and identity based key management and authentication for wireless ad hoc networks](#)," in International conference on information technology: Coding and Computing (ITCC's 04), Las Vegas, Nevada, April 2004, pp. 1-5.
- [6] Y. Zhang, W. Liu, W. Lou and Y. Fang, "Securing mobile ad hoc networks with certificateless public keys," IEEE Transaction on Dependable and Secure Computing, Vol. 3, No. 4, Dec. 2006, pp. 386-399.
- [7] H. Harney, C. Muckenhirn, "[Group key management protocol \(GKMP\) architecture](#)", Network Working Group, July 1997. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc2094>. [Accessed: Jan. 1, 2018].
- [8] H. Harney, C. Muckenhirn, "[Group Key Management Protocol\(GKMP\) Specification](#)", Internet Request for Comments 2093, July 1997. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc2093>. [Accessed: Jan. 1, 2018].
- [9] H. Harney, U. Meth, A. Colegrove and G. Gross, "[Group Secure Association Key Management Protocol\(GKMP\)](#)", Internet Request for Comments 4535, June 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc4535>. [Accessed: Jan. 1, 2018].
- [10] B. Weis, S. Rowles and T. Hardjono, "[The Group Domain of Interpretation\(GDOI\)](#)", Internet Request for Comments 6407, Oct. 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc6407>. [Accessed: Jan. 1, 2018].
- [11] Bryans, J. W., Fitzgerald and J. S., "[Formal engineering of XACML access control policies in VDM++](#)," in International Conference on Formal Engineering Methods, Florida, USA, Berlin, Heidelberg, Nov. 2007, pp. 37-56.

- [12] K. Fislser, S. Krishnamurthi, L. A. Meyerovich and M. C. Tschantz, "[Verification and change-impact analysis of access control policies](#)," in Proc. of 27th International Conference on Software Engineering, MO, USA, May 2005, pp. 196-205.
- [13] D. Jackson, , [Software Abstractions: Logic, Languages, and Analysis](#), MIT Press, ISBN: 978-0-262-10114-1, 2006. .
- [14] D. Jackson, "[Micromodels of Software: Lightweight Modelling and Analysis with Alloy](#)," MIT Lab, Jan. 2002. [Online]. Available: <https://courses.cs.washington.edu/courses/cse503/04sp/readings/alloy-ref.pdf>. [Accessed: Jan. 1, 2018].
- [15] D. Jackson, "[Alloy: a lightweight object modelling notation](#)," ACM Trans. Soft. Eng. Methodol., Vol. 11, No. 2, April 2002, pp. 256-290.
- [16] V. Chandola, A. Banerjee and V. Kumar, "[Anomaly Detection: A Survey](#)," ACM computing surveys, Vol. 41, No. 3, 2009, pp. 1-72.
- [17] Y. Zhang, N. Meratnia and P. Havinga, "[Outlier Detection Techniques for Wireless Sensor Networks: A Survey](#)," IEEE Communication Surveys & Tutorials, Vol. 12, No. 2, 2010, pp. 159-170.
- [18] P. Gogoi, B. Borah and D. K. Bhattacharyya, "[Anomaly Detection Analysis of Intrusion Data using Supervised and Unsupervised Approach](#)," Journal of Convergence Information Technology, Vol. 5, No. 1, Feb. 2010, pp. 95-110.
- [19] P. Gogoi, D. K. Bhattacharyya, B. Borah and J. K. Kalita, "[A Survey of Outlier Detection Methods in Network Anomaly Identification](#)," The Computer Journal, Vol. 54, No. 4, April 2011, pp. 570-588.
- [20] D. M. Hawkin, Identification of Outliers, London: Chapman and Hall, 1980.
- [21] V. A. Traag, A. Browet, F. Calabrese and F. Morlot, "[Social Event Detection in Massive Mobile Phone Data Using Probabilistic Location Interference](#)," in SocialCom/PASSAT, 9-11 October 2011.
- [22] B. Krishnamachari and S. Iyengar, "[Distributed Bayesian algorithms for fault tolerant event region detection in wireless sensor networks](#)," IEEE Transactions on Computers, Vol. 53, No. 3, March 2004, pp. 241-250.
- [23] F. Martincic and L. Schwiebert, "Distributed event detection in sensor networks," in Proceedings of Systems and Network Communication, French, Polynesia, Nov. 2006, pp. 1-6.
- [24] M. Ding, D. Chen, K. Xing and X. Cheng, "[Localized fault tolerant event boundary detection in sensor networks](#)," in IEEE conference of computer and communications societies, Florida, USA, March 2005, pp. 902-913.

- [25] A. P. R. Silva, M. H. T. Martins, B. P. S. Rocha, A. A. F. Loureiro, L. B. Ruiz and H. C. Wong, "[Decentralized intrusion detection in wireless sensor networks](#)," 1st ACM international workshop on Quality of Service and Security in Wireless., Quebec, Canada Oct. 2005, pp. 16-23.
- [26] J. Chen, S. Kher and A. Somani, "[Distributed fault detection of wireless sensor networks](#)," Proceedings of the 2006 workshop on dependability issues in wireless ad hoc networks and sensor networks, CA, USA, Sep. 2006, pp. 65-72.
- [27] X. Luo, M. Dong and Y. Huang, "[On distributed fault tolerant detection in wireless sensor networks](#)," IEEE Transactions on computers, Vol. 55, No.1, Jan. 2006 pp. 58-70.
- [28] J. Raja, X. R. Wang, O. Obst and P. Valencia, "[Wireless sensor network anomalies: Diagnosis and detection strategies](#)," Intelligence-Based Systems Engineering, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011, pp. 309-325.
- [29] W. Hu, T. Tan, L. Wang and S. Maybank, "[A survey on visual surveillance of object motion and behaviors](#)," IEEE transavtion, Vol. 34, No. 3, July 2004, pp. 334-352.
- [30] D. M. Hawkins, Identification of outliers, London: Chapman and Hall, 1980.
- [31] E. M. Knorr and R. T. Ng, "[Algorithm for mining distance based outliers in large datasets](#)," 24th international conference on very large databases, New York, USA, 1998, pp. 392-403.
- [32] M. M. Breunig, H. P. Kriegel, R. T. Ng and J. Sander, "[LOF: Identifying Density Based Local Outliers](#)," ACM SIGMOD, Dallas, TX, USA, May 2000, pp. 93-104.
- [33] B. Wang and W. Perrizo, "[RDF: a density-based outlier detection method using vertical data representation](#)," in Fourth IEEE International Conference on Data Mining, Nov. 2004, pp. 1-4.
- [34] S. Rajagopalan, R. Karwoski, B. Bartholmai and R. Robb, "Quantitative image analytics for stratified pulmonary medicine," in IEEE Int. Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI), Barcelona, Spain, May 2012, pp. 1779-1782.
- [35] J. W. Branch, C. Giannelia, B. Szymanski, R. Wolff and H. Kargupta, "[In-network outlier detection in wireless sensor networks](#)," Knowledge and information systems, Vol. 34, No. 1, Jan. 2013, pp. 23-54.
- [36] H. Ayadi, A. Zouinkhi and B. Boussaid, "[A Machine Learning Methods: Outlier detection in WSN](#)," in 16th international conference on Sciences and Techniques of Automatic control, Monastir, Tunisia, December 2015, pp. 722-727.
- [37] C. Titouna, M. Aliouat and M. Gueroui, "Outlier Detection Approach Using Bayes Classifiers," Wireless Pers. Communications, Vol. 85, No. 3, June 2015, pp. 1009-1023.
- [38] J. C. M. Teo and C. H. Tan, "[Energy-efficient and scalable group key agreement for large ad hoc networks](#)," in Proceedings of the 2nd ACM international workshop on Performance evaluation of wireless ad hoc, sensor, and ubiquitous networks, Quebec, Canada, October 2005, pp. 114-121.

- [39] E. W. Dijkstra, "[A note on two problems in connexion with graphs](#)," Numerische Mathematik, Vol. 1, No. 1, December 1959, pp. 269-271.
- [40] J. Spinrad, "Recognition of circle graphs," Journal of Algorithms, Vol. 16, No. 2, March 1994, pp. 264-282.
- [41] W. J. Gutjahr, "[A graph-based Ant System and its convergence](#)," Future Generation Computer Systems, Vol. 16, No. 9, June 2000, pp. 873-888.
- [42] A. Shamir, "[How to share a secret](#)," Communications of the ACM, Vol. 22, No. 11, November 1979, pp. 612-613.
- [43] J. V. D. Merwe, D. Dowoud and S. McDonald, "[A Survey on Peer to Peer key management for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks](#)," ACM Computing Surveys, Vol. 39, No. 1, Article 1, April 2007, pp. 1-45.
- [44] "The Network Simulator - ns-2," [Online]. Available: <https://www.isi.edu/nsnam/ns/>. [Accessed 18 7 2018].
- [45] "[scipy.cluster.hierarchy.dendrogram.html](#)," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/generated/scipy.cluster.hierarchy.dendrogram.html>. [Accessed 18 7 2018].
- [46] A. Kumar, K. Gopal and A. Aggarwal, "Novel Trusted Hierarchy Construction for RFID Sensor-Based MANETs Using ECCs," ETRI Journal, Vol. 37, No. 1, July 2015, pp. 186-196.
- [47] A. Kumar, K. Gopal and A. Aggarwal, "[Simulation and analysis of authentication protocols for mobile Internet of Things \(MIoT\)](#)," 2014 IEEE International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Grid Computing (PDGC), JUIT, Wagnaghat, India, 2014, pp.423-428.
- [48] A. Kumar, K. Gopal and A. Aggarwal, "[Design and Analysis of Lightweight Trust Mechanism for Accessing Data in MANETs](#)," KSII Transactions on Internet & Information Systems, Vol. 8, No. 3, March 2014, pp. 1119-1143.
- [49] A. Kumar, K. Gopal and A. Aggarwal, "[Cost and Lightweight Modeling Analysis of RFID Authentication Protocols in Resource Constraint Internet of Things](#)," Journal of Communications Software and Systems, Vol. 10, No. 3, September 2014, pp. 179-143.
- [50] A. Kumar, K. Gopal and A. Aggarwal, "[A complete, efficient and lightweight cryptography solution for resource constraints Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks](#)," 2nd IEEE International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Grid Computing (PDGC), JUIT, Wagnaghat, India, Feb. 2013, pp. 854-860.
- [51] A. Kumar, K. Gopal and A. Aggarwal, "[Design and Analysis of Lightweight Trust Mechanism for Secret Data using Lightweight Cryptographic Primitives in MANETs](#)," IJ Network Security, Vol. 18, No. 1, Jan. 2016, pp.1-18.

- [52] A. Kumar, K. Gopal and A. Aggarwal, "[A novel lightweight key management scheme for RFID-sensor integrated hierarchical MANET based on internet of things](#)", International Journal of Advanced Intelligence Paradigms, Vol. 9, No. 2-3, 2017, pp. 220-245.
- [53] N. Chugh, A. Kumar and A. Aggarwal, "[Security aspects of a RFID-sensor integrated low-powered devices for internet-of-things](#)", 2016 Fourth International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Grid Computing (PDGC), JUIT, Wagnaghat, India, Dec. 2016, pp. 759-763.

AUTHORS

Neeraj Chugh is an Assistant Professor in University of Petroleum & Energy Studies, Dehradun, India and enrolled in PhD (CSE) from Uttarakhand Technical University (UTU), Uttarakhand, India. He received his M. Tech. (CSE) from Kurukshetra University Kurukshetra, India in 2001. His research interests includes Database Management system, Data Mining, and Outlier/Anomaly detection and event detection in sensor networks.

Adarsh Kumar received his ME degree in Software Engineering from Thapar University, Patiala, Punjab, India, in 2005 and earned his PhD degree from JIIT university, Noida, India in 2016 followed by Post Doctoral from AIT, Ireland during 2016-2018. From 2005 to 2016, he has been associated with the Department of Computer Science Engineering & Information Technology, Jaypee Institute of Information Technology, Noida, UttarPardesh, India, where he worked as Assistant Professor. Currently he is working with University of Petroleum & Energy Studies, Dehradun, India as Associate Professor in CSE department. His main research interests are cryptography, network security, and adhoc networks.

Alok Aggarwal received his bachelors' and masters' degrees in Computer Science & Engineering in 1995 and 2001 respectively and his PhD degree in Engineering from IITRoorkee, Roorkee, India in 2010. He has academic experience of 18 years, industry experience of 4 years and research experience of 5 years. He has contributed more than 150 research contributions in different journals and conference proceedings. Currently he is working with University of Petroleum & Energy Studies, Dehradun, India as Professor in CSE department. His main research interests are wired/wireless networks, security, and coding theory.

IMPROVEMENT of MULTIPLE ROUTING BASED on FUZZY CLUSTERING and PSO ALGORITHM IN WSNs TO REDUCE ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Gholamreza Farahani

Department of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology, Iranian Research Organization for Science and Technology (IROST), Tehran, Iran

ABSTRACT

One of the most important issues discussed in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) is how to transfer information from nodes within the network to the base station and select the best possible route for transmission of this information, taking into account energy consumption for the network lifetime with maximum reliability and security. Hence, it would be useful to provide a suitable method that would have the features mentioned. This paper uses an Ad-hoc On-demand Multipath Distance Vector (AOMDV) as a routing protocol. This protocol has high energy consumption due to its multipath. However, it is a big challenge if it can reduce AOMDV energy consumption. Therefore, clustering operations for nodes are of high priority to determine the head of clusters which LEACH protocol and fuzzy logic and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm are used for this purpose. Simulation results represent 5% improvement in energy consumption in a WSN compared to AOMDV method.

KEYWORDS

Energy Aware Routing Protocol, Fuzzy Logic, Ad-hoc Multipath, LEACH, Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijenc/V10N6/10618cnc06.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijc2018.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Heinzelman, W. R., Chandrakasan, A. & Balakrishnan, H., (2000) “[Energy-Efficient Communication Protocol for Wireless Microsensor Networks](#)”, Proceedings of the Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 4-7 January, Maui, Hawaii.
- [2] Houda, L. (2010) Wireless ad hoc and Sensor Networks, Vol. 6, John Wiley & Sons.
- [3] Marina, M. K. & Das, S. R., (2001) “[On-demand Multipath Distance Vector Routing for Ad Hoc Networks](#)”, Proceeding of 9th IEEE International Conference on Network Protocols, pp14-23, Riverside, 11-14 November, California, USA.
- [4] Amine, D. A., Kamel, A. M. & Bouabdellah, K., (2014) “[Formal Verification of a New Version of AOMDV in ad hoc Network](#)”, *Procedia Computer Science*, Vol. 37, pp160-167.
- [5] Dam, M. T., Nguyen, V. C., Nguyen, T. T. & Tran Le, T. D., (2014) “Low-Power and High-Performance Design for Cryptosystem Using Power Aware and Pipeline Techniques”, International Conference on Advanced Technologies for Communications (ATC), 15-17 October, Hanoi, Vietnam.
- [6] Kevin, J. (2009) [Security and Privacy Controls for Federal Information Systems and Organizations](#), Revision 3, NIST SP. 800–53.
- [7] Nguyen, T. T., Nguyen, V. C. & Pham, H. M., (2012) “Enhance the performance and security of SOC using pipeline and dynamic partial reconfiguration”, International Conference on Integrated Circuits and Devices in Vietnam (ICDV), 13-15 August, Danang, Vietnam.
- [8] Rages, G. K. & Baskaran, K., (2012) “[A Survey on Futuristic Health Care System: WBANs](#)”, *Procedia Engineering*, Vol. 30, pp889–896.
- [9] Singh, R. & Verma, A. K., (2017) “Energy efficient cross layer based adaptive threshold routing protocol for WSN”, *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, Vol. 72, pp166-173.
- [10] Ke, W., Yangrui, O., Hong, J., Heli, Z. & Xi, L., (2016) “[Energy aware hierarchical cluster-based routing protocol for WSNs](#)”, *The Journal of China Universities of Posts and Telecommunications*, Vol. 23, Issue 4, pp46-52.
- [11] Yigit, M., Gungor, V. C., Fadel, E., Nassef, L., Akkari, N. & Akyildiz, I. F., (2016) “Channel-aware routing and priority-aware multi-channel scheduling for WSN-based smart grid applications”, *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, Vol. 71, pp50-58.
- [12] Mohamed, R. E., Saleh, A. I., Abdelrazzak, M. & Samra, A. S., (2017) “Energy-Efficient Routing Protocols for Solving Energy Hole Problem in Wireless Sensor Networks”, *Computer Networks*, Vol. 114, pp51-66.

- [13] Vimalarani, C., Subramanian, R. & Sivanandam, S. N., (2016) "[An Enhanced PSO-Based Clustering Energy Optimization Algorithm for Wireless Sensor Network](#)", The Scientific World Journal, Vol. 2016.
- [14] Kuila, P. & Jana, P. K., (2014) "[Energy efficient clustering and routing algorithms for wireless sensor networks: Particle swarm optimization approach](#)", Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence, Vol. 33, pp127–140.
- [15] Balaji, S., Golden Julie, E., Rajaram, M. & Harold Robinson Y., (2016) "[Fuzzy Based Particle Swarm Optimization Routing Technique for Load Balancing in Wireless Sensor Networks](#)", International Journal of Computer, Electrical, Automation, Control and Information Engineering, Vol. 10, No. 7, pp1418-1427.
- [16] Tang, J., Liu, A., Zhang, J., Xiong, N. N., Zeng, Z. & Wang, T., (2018) "[A Trust-Based Secure Routing Scheme Using the Traceback Approach for Energy-Harvesting Wireless Sensor Networks](#)", Sensors, Vol. 18, No. 3, pp1-44.
- [17] Fardin Far, S. & Alaei, M., (2018) "[A New Method to Reduce Energy Consumption in Manet Network Routing based on OLSR Protocol and Genetic Algorithm](#)", Journal of Advances in Computer Research, Vol. 9, No. 3, pp55-70.
- [18] Jacquet, P., Muhlethaler, P., Clausen, T., Laouiti, A., Qayyum, A. and Viennot, L., (2001) "[Optimized Link State Routing Protocol for Ad Hoc Networks](#)", Proceedings IEEE International Multi Topic Conference (INMIC), 30-30 December, Lahore, Pakistan.
- [19] Li, L. & Li, D., (2018) "[An Energy-Balanced Routing Protocol for a Wireless Sensor Network](#)", Journal of Sensors, Vol. 2018.
- [20] Arthur, D. & Vassilvitskii, S., (2007) "[k-Means plus plus: the advantages of careful seeding](#)", Proceedings of the 18th Annual Acm-Siam Symposium on Discrete Algorithms, New Orleans, LA, USA, 7-9 January, pp1027–1035.
- [21] Heinzelman, W. B., Chandrakasan, A. P. & Balakrishnan, H., (2002) "[An application-specific protocol architecture for wireless microsensor networks](#)", IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, Vol. 1, No. 4, pp660–670.
- [22] Tewari, M. & Vaisla, K. S., (2014) "[Performance study of SEP and DEC hierarchical clustering algorithm for heterogeneous WSN](#)," International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Communication Networks, Bhopal, India, 14-16 November, pp385–389.
- [23] Kamran Khan, M., Shiraz, M., Ghafoor, K. Z., Khan, S., Safaa Sadiq, A. & Ahmed, G., (2018) "[EE-MRP: Energy-Efficient Multistage Routing Protocol for Wireless Sensor Networks](#)", Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing, Vol. 2018.
- [24] Tang, Y. J., Lee, C. W., Lin, M. H., Liu, B. H. & Tsai M. J., (2017) "Energy consumption reduction methods of geographic routing protocols with out-of-date location information in mobile ad hoc networks", IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), 21-25 May, Paris, France.

- [25] Ogawa, E., Nakamura, S., Enokido, T. & Takizawa, M., (2017) “An Energy-aware One-to-one Routing Protocol in Wireless Ad-hoc Network”, Proceeding of the 20th International Conference on Network-Based Information Systems (NBiS), 24–26 August, Toronto, Canada, pp1162-1168.
- [26] Ogawa, E., Nakamura, S., Enokido, T. and Takizawa, M., (2017) “A Low-energy Unicast Ad-hoc Routing Protocol in Wireless Networks”, Proceeding of the 12th International Conference on Broad-Band Wireless Computing, Communication and Applications (BWCCA), 8–10 November, Barcelona, Spain, pp1162-1168.
- [27] Ogawa, E., Nakamura, S. & Takizawa, M., (2017) “An Energy-saving Unicast Routing Protocol in Wireless Ad-hoc Network”, Proceeding of the 11th International Conference on Innovative Mobile and Internet Services in Ubiquitous Computing (IMIS), 10-12 July, Torino, Italy, pp1162-1168.
- [28] gawa, E., Nakamura, S., Enokido, T. & Takizawa, M., (2018) “Unicast Routing Protocols to Reduce Electric Energy Consumption in Wireless Ad-Hoc Networks”, 32nd International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications Workshops (WAINA), Krakow, Poland, 16-18 May.
- [29] Patra, R. R. & Patra, P. K., (2011) [“Analysis of k-Coverage in Wireless Sensor Networks”](#), International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, Vol. 2, No. 9, pp91-96.

AUTHOR

Gholamreza Farahani received his BSc degree in electrical engineering from Sharif University of Technology, Tehran, Iran, in 1998 and MSc and PhD degrees in electrical engineering from Amirkabir University of Technology (Polytechnic), Tehran, Iran in 2000 and 2006 respectively. Currently, he is an assistant professor in the Institute of Electrical and Information Technology, Iranian Research Organization for Science and Technology (IROST), Iran. His research interest is computer networks especially routing.

A PROACTIVE FLOW ADMISSION AND RE-ROUTING SCHEME FOR LOAD BALANCING AND MITIGATION OF CONGESTION PROPAGATION IN SDN DATA PLANE

Smimesh C. N.¹, Grace Mary Kanaga E.², and Ranjitha K.³

^{1&3} Dept. of Computer Science and Engineering, Govt. Engineering College, Thrissur, India

² Dept. of Computer Science and Engineering, Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Coimbatore, India

ABSTRACT

The centralized architecture in software-defined network (SDN) provides a global view of the underlying network, paving the way for enormous research in the area of SDN traffic engineering (SDN TE). This research focuses on the load balancing aspects of SDN TE, given that the existing reactive methods for data-plane load balancing eventually result in packet loss and proactive schemes for data plane load balancing do not address congestion propagation. In the proposed work, the SDN controller periodically monitors flow level statistics and utilization on each link in the network and over-utilized links that cause network congestion and packet loss are identified as bottleneck links. For load balancing the identified largest flow and further traffic through these bottleneck links are rerouted through the lightly-loaded alternate path. The proposed scheme models a Bayesian Network using the observed port utilization and residual bandwidth to decide whether the newly computed alternate path can handle the new flow load before flow admission which in turn reduces congestion propagation. The simulation results show that when the network traffic increases the proposed method efficiently re-routes the flows and balance the network load which substantially improves the network efficiency and the quality of service (QoS) parameters.

KEYWORDS

Bayesian Network, QoS, SDN, Traffic Engineering, Congestion Propagation.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcnc/V10N6/10618cnc07.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijc2018.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Ian F. Akyildiz, Ahyoung Lee, Pu Wang, Min Luo, and Wu Chou, ['Research Challenges for Traffic Engineering in Software Defined Networks'](#), IEEE Network, 2016, 30, pp.~52—58
- [2] Kreutz, Ramos, Esteves Verissimo P, Esteve Rothenberg C, Azodolmolky S, and Uhlig S, ['Software-Defined Networking: A Comprehensive Survey'](#), Proceedings of the IEEE, 2015, 103, pp.~14—76
- [3] Sang Min Park, Seungbum Ju, Jaiyong Lee, ['Efficient routing for traffic offloading in Software-defined Network'](#), Procedia ComputerScience,2014, 34, pp.~ 674—679
- [4] C. N. Sminesh, E. Grace Mary Kanaga, K. Ranjitha, ['Flow monitoring scheme for reducing congestion and packet loss in software defined networks'](#), 2017 4th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems (ICACCS), 2017, pp.~ 1—5
- [5] 'Openflow switch specification V1.4.0 (Wire Protocol 0x05)', <https://www.opennetworking.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/openflow-spec-v1.4.0.pdf> , accessed October 14, 2013
- [6] Kanagavelu Renuga, and Khin Mi Mi Aung, ['SDN Controlled Local Re-routing to Reduce Congestion in Cloud Data Center'](#), International Conference on Cloud Computing Research and Innovation (ICCCRI) IEEE., 26-27 Oct. 2015
- [7] Akyildiz, I., Lee, A., Wang, P., Luo, M. and Chou, W, ['A roadmap for traffic engineering in SDN-OpenFlow networks'](#), Computer Networks, 2014,71, pp.~1--30.
- [8] Xiaoyuan Lu, Yanwei Xu ['SFabric: A Scalable SDN Based Large Layer 2 Data Center Network Fabric'](#), {Cluster Computing(2018)}.<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-018-2399-1>, Springer US
- [9] Braun, W. and Menth, M., ['Software-Defined Networking Using OpenFlow: Protocols, Applications and Architectural Design Choices'](#), Future Internet, 2014, 6(2), pp.~302—336
- [10] ['Software-Defined-Networking: The New Norm for Networks ONF White Paper'](#) <https://www.opennetworking.org/images/stories/downloads/sdnresources/white-papers/wp-sdn-newnorm.pdf>, accessed on April 13, 2012
- [11] Lantz B, Heller B, McKeown N ['A network in a laptop : rapid prototyping for Software Defined networks'](#), Proceedings of the 9th ACM SIGCOMM WORKSHOP ON Hot Topics in Networks,2010 October
- [12] Alessio Botta, Walter de Donato, Alberto Dainotti, Stefano Avallone, and Antonio Pescape, 'D-ITG 2.8.1 Manual' University of Napoli Federico II [http:// traffic.comics.unina.it/software/ITG](http://traffic.comics.unina.it/software/ITG), October 28, 2013

- [13] Byungjoon Lee, Sae Hyong Park, Jisoo Shin, and Sunhee Yang, ['IRIS: The Openflow-based Recursive SDN Controller'](#), ICACT 2014 :1237-1240
- [14] Larry L. Peterson, Bruce S. Davie ['Computer Networks a Systems Approach'](#), Elsevier, 2007, 4th edition
- [15] Mohan, Purnima Murali, Tram Truong-Huu, and Mohan Gurusamy , ['TCAM-aware Local Rerouting for Fast and Efficient Failure Recovery in Software Defined Networks'](#), IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM),2015
- [16] Pfaff B, Pettit J, Koponen T, Jackson E, Zhou A, Rajahalme J, Gross J, Wang A, Stringer J, Shelar P, Amidon K , ['The design and implementation of open switch'](#), 12th USENIX symposium on networked systems design and implementation (NSDI 15).2015
- [17] Peter Megyesi , Alessio Botta, Giuseppe Aceto, Antonio Pescape, Sandor Molnar, ['Available Bandwidth Measurement in Software Defined Networks'](#), Proceedings of the 31st Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing ,April 04 - 08, 2016, Pisa, Italy
- [18] Kao, Ming-Tsung, (2016), ['An Effective Routing Mechanism for Link Congestion Avoidance in Software-Defined Networking'](#), Computer Symposium (ICS), 2016 International. IEEE,2016
- [19] Gholami, Masoumeh, and Behzad Akbari, ['Congestion control in software defined data center networks through flow rerouting'](#), Electrical Engineering (ICEE), 2015 23rd Iranian Conference on.IEEE, 2015
- [20] Hwang and Jaehyun, ['Scalable Congestion Control Protocol Based on SDN in Data Center Networks'](#), Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM), 2015 IEEE, IEEE, 2015.
- [21] Attarha and Shadi, ['A load balanced congestion aware routing mechanism for Software Defined Networks'](#),Electrical Engineering (ICEE), 2017 Iranian Conference on. IEEE, IEEE, 2017.
- [22] Ahmed Al-Jawad, Ramona Trestian, Purav Shah and Orhan Gemikonakli, ['BaProbSDN: A Probabilistic-based QoS Routing Mechanism for Software Defined Networks'](#), 1st IEEE Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 04 June 2015
- [23] Turgay Korkmaz and Marwan Krunz, ['Bandwidth-Delay Constrained Path Selection Under Inaccurate State Information'](#), IEEE/ACM Transaction on Networking, 2003, 11, pp.~384—398
- [24] Richard E. Neapolitan, ['Introduction to Bayesian Networks in Learning Bayesian Networks'](#), Prentice Hall, 2004.
- [25] James F Kurose, Keith Ross, ['Computer Networking A Top-down approach'](#) Fifth Edition, Pearson Education, 2014.

- [26] Thomas H Coren, Charles E Leiserson, Ronald L Rivest and Clifford Stein, ['Introduction to Algorithms'](#), 2, The MIT Press, 2001
- [27] J. Mela, ['Emulation of Abilene Network using DETER'](#) TRUST Research Experiences for Undergraduates (TRUST-REU) in Cyber Security and Trustworthy Systems (2010)
- [28] C.E. Hopps, ['Analysis of an Equal-Cost Multi-Path Algorithm'](#), RFC 2992, Tech. Rep., November 2000.
- [29] M. Al-Fares et al., ['Hedera: Dynamic Flow Scheduling for Data Center Networks'](#), Proc. Networked Systems Design and Implementation Symp.,10, Apr. 2010, p. 19.
- [30] A. R. Curtis, W. Kim, and P. Yalagandula, ['Mahout: Low-Overhead Datacenter Traffic Management Using End-Host-Based Elephant Detection'](#), Proc. 30th IEEE INFOCOM '11, Apr. 2011, pp. ~1629--37.
- [31] S. Agarwal, M. Kodialam, T. Lakshman, ['Traffic engineering in software defined networks'](#), Proceedings of the 32nd IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications , INFOCOM'13, April 2013, pp.~ 2211--2219.
- [32] S. Knight, H. Nguyen, N. Falkner, R. Bowden, and M. Roughan, 'The Internet Topology Zoo',IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, 29,2011 , pp. 1765—1775
- [33] Y. Jarraya, T. Madi, and M. Debbabi, ['A survey and a layered taxonomy of software-defined networking'](#), Communications Surveys Tutorials, IEEE}, 2014, 99, pp. 1—1
- [34] OpenFlow Switch Specification Version 1.5.0 (Protocol version 0x06) December 19,2014 Copyright:2014;OpenNetworkingFoundation,https://www.opennetworking.org/images/stories/downloads/sdn-resources/onf-specifications/openflow/openflow-switch-v1.5.0.noipr.pdf
- [35] Raj, P. Herbert, and SV Kasmir Raja. ['Identifying Congestion hot spots in MPLS using Bayesian network.'](#) Asian Journal of Information Technology, 6, 2007: 854--858.
- [36] S. Baik, Y. Lim, J. Kim, and Y. Lee, ['Adaptive flow monitoring in SDN architecture'](#), 17th Asia-Pacific Network Operations and Management Symposium (APNOMS), 2015, pp. 468—470

AUTHORS

Sminesh C. N. received his ME degree from Birla Institute of Technology, Ranchi, India in the year 2003. He is working as Associate Professor in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Government Engineering College Thrissur. His research interests include Traffic Engineering in SDN, Next Generation Internet Architecture. He is the author of more than 15 research articles published in national and international conferences

Grace Mary Kanaga E. received her PhD in Computer Science and Engineering from Anna University Coimbatore, India in the year 2011. She is working as an Associate Professor in Computer Sciences Technology Department, Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Coimbatore. Her research interests are Big Data Analytics, Computational Intelligence, Software Agents, Networks and Distributed Systems. She has published more than 45 papers in National and International Conferences, International Journals and Book chapters.

Ranjitha K. received her ME degree from Government Engineering College Thrissur, India in the year 2016. Presently she is a Senior Research Fellow, CR Rao AIMSCS, University of Hyderabad Campus, Hyderabad, India. Her research interests include Information Security and Future Internet. She has seven years of Industry experience and author of several research articles.

ENSEMBLE OF PROBABILISTIC LEARNING NETWORKS FOR IOT EDGE INTRUSION DETECTION

Tony Jan and A.S.M Sajeev

Melbourne Institute of Technology, Australia

ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an intelligent and compact machine learning model for IoT intrusion detection using an ensemble of semi-parametric models with Ada boost. The proposed model provides an adequate real time intrusion detection at an affordable computational complexity suitable for the IoT edge networks. The proposed model is evaluated against other comparable models using the benchmark data on IoT-IDS and shows comparable performance with reduced computations as required.

KEYWORDS

Adaboosted ensemble learning, IoT edge security, machine learning for IoT

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcnc/V10N6/10618cnc08.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijc2018.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Muhammad Umar Farooq, Muhammad Waseem, Anjum Khairi, and Sadia Mazhar, (2015) "[A critical analysis on the security concerns of internet of things \(IoT\)](#)", International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 111, No. 7.
- [2] Manos Antonakakis, Tim April, Michael Bailey, Matt Bernhard, Elie Bursztein, Jaime Cochran, Zakir Durumeric, J Alex Halderman, Luca Invernizzi, Michalis Kallitsis, et al., (2017) "[Understanding the mirai botnet](#)", in USENIX Security Symposium.
- [3] Antonio Brogi and Stefano Forti, (2017) "QoS-aware deployment of IoT applications through the fog", IEEE Internet of Things Journal, Vol. 4, No. 5, pp. 1185–1192.
- [4] Farhoud Hosseinpour, Payam Vahdani Amoli, Juha Plosila, Timo Hamäläinen, and Hannu Tenhunen, (2016) "[An Intrusion Detection System for Fog Computing and IoT based Logistic Systems using a Smart Data Approach](#)", International Journal of Digital Content Technology and its Applications, Vol. 10.
- [5] Bernard W Silverman, (2018) Density estimation for statistics and data analysis, Routledge.
- [6] Ron Kohavi, David H Wolpert, et al., (1996) "[Bias plus variance decomposition for zero-one loss functions](#)", in ICML, Vol. 96, pp. 275–83.
- [7] Yair Meidan, Michael Bohadana, Yael Mathov, Yisroel Mirsky, Dominik Breitenbacher, Asaf Shabtai, and Yuval Elovici, (2018) "[N-BaIoT: Network-based Detection of IoT Botnet Attacks Using Deep Autoencoders](#)", arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.03409.
- [8] Alya Geogiana Buja, Shekh Faisal Abdul-Latip, and Rabiah Ahmad, (2018) "[A Security Analysis of IoT Encryption: Side-channel Cube Attack on Simeck32/64](#)", arXiv preprint arXiv:1808.03557.
- [9] Ryan Williams, Emma McMahon, Sagar Samtani, Mark Patton, and Hsinchun Chen, (2017) "[Identifying vulnerabilities of consumer Internet of Things \(IoT\) devices: A scalable approach](#)", in Intelligence and Security Informatics (ISI), 2017 IEEE International Conference on, pp. 179–181.
- [10] Sudhi R Sinha and Youngchoon Park, (2017) Building an Effective IoT Ecosystem for Your Business, Springer.
- [11] Briana Arrington, LiEsa Barnett, Rahmira Rufus, and Albert Esterline, (2016) "[Behavioral modeling intrusion detection system \(bmids\) using internet of things \(iot\) behavior-based anomaly detection via immunity-inspired algorithms](#)", in Computer Communication and Networks (ICCCN), 2016 25th International Conference on, pp. 1–6.
- [12] Otavio Carvalho, Manuel Garcia, Eduardo Roloff, Emmanuell Diaz Carreño, and Philippe OA Navaux, (2017) "[IoT Workload Distribution Impact Between Edge and Cloud Computing in a Smart Grid Application](#)", in Latin American High Performance Computing Conference, pp. 203–217.
- [13] Eduardo Cuervo, Aruna Balasubramanian, Dae ki Cho, Alec Wolman, Stefan Saroiu, Ranveer Chandra, and Paramvir Bahl, (2010) "[MAUI: making smartphones last longer with code offload](#)", in Proceedings of the 8th international conference on Mobile systems, applications, and services, pp. 49–62.

- [14] Mark S Gordon, Davoud Anoushe Jamshidi, Scott A Mahlke, Zhuoqing Morley Mao, and Xu Chen, (2012) “[COMET: Code Offload by Migrating Execution Transparently.](#)”, in OSDI, Vol. 12, pp. 93–106.
- [15] Sokol Kosta, Andrius Aucinas, Pan Hui, Richard Mortier, and Xinwen Zhang, (2012) “[Thinkair: Dynamic resource allocation and parallel execution in the cloud for mobile code offloading](#)”, in Infocom, 2012 Proceedings IEEE, pp. 945–953.
- [16] Takayuki Nishio, Ryoichi Shinkuma, Tatsuro Takahashi, and Narayan B Mandayam, (2013) “[Service-oriented heterogeneous resource sharing for optimizing service latency in mobile cloud](#)”, in Proceedings of the first international workshop on Mobile cloud computing & networking, pp. 19–26.
- [17] Elike Hodo, Xavier Bellekens, Andrew Hamilton, Pierre-Louis Dubouilh, Ephraim Iorkyase, Christos Tachtatzis, and Robert Atkinson, (2016) “[Threat analysis of IoT networks using artificial neural network intrusion detection system](#)”, in Networks, Computers and Communications (ISNCC), 2016 International Symposium on, pp. 1–6.
- [18] Nof Abuzainab, Walid Saad, Choong-Seon Hong, and H Vincent Poor, (2017) “[Cognitive hierarchy theory for distributed resource allocation in the internet of things](#)”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1703.07418.
- [19] Abdulla Amin Aburomman and Mamun Bin Ibne Reaz, (2016) “[A novel SVM-kNN-PSO ensemble method for intrusion detection system](#)”, Applied Soft Computing, Vol. 38, pp. 360–372.
- [20] Wathiq Laftah Al-Yaseen, Zulaiha Ali Othman, and Mohd Zakree Ahmad Nazri, (2017) “[Multi-level hybrid support vector machine and extreme learning machine based on modified K-means for intrusion detection system](#)”, Expert Systems with Applications, Vol. 67, pp. 296–303.
- [21] Milad Yousefi, Moslem Yousefi, Ricardo Poley Martins Ferreira, Joong Hoon Kim, and Flavio S Fogliatto, (2018) “[Chaotic genetic algorithm and Adaboost ensemble metamodeling approach for optimum resource planning in emergency departments](#)”, Artificial intelligence in medicine, Vol. 84, pp. 23–33.
- [22] YANG Xinwu, M A Zhuang, and YUAN Shun, (2016) “[Multi-class Adaboost Algorithm Based on the Adjusted Weak Classifier](#)”, Journal of Electronics & Information Technology, Vol. 38, No. 2, pp. 373–380.
- [23] Anthony Zaknich, (1998) “[Introduction to the modified probabilistic neural network for general signal processing applications](#)”, IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing, Vol. 46, No. 7, pp. 1980–1990.
- [24] Elike Hodo, Xavier Bellekens, Andrew Hamilton, Pierre-Louis Dubouilh, Ephraim Iorkyase, Christos Tachtatzis, and Robert Atkinson, (2016) “[Threat analysis of IoT networks using artificial neural network intrusion detection system](#)”, in Networks, Computers and Communications (ISNCC), 2016 International Symposium on, pp. 1–6.